

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Bogabordhan: a stable, high-yielding, low-input traditional variety of Assam, India

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Northeastern India is endowed with many landraces of rice that are adapted specifically to the harsh, varying rainfed environments of the region. These varieties are the results of selections made by farmers. Farmers prefer varieties that have reasonably high levels of relative productivity and stability under management situations with little or no inputs.

We evaluated the performance of 20 local varieties selected from sali (wet season [WS]) germplasm stock maintained at the RARS, based on their phenotypic acceptability for three consecutive wet seasons from 1988 to 1990. Their performance was compared with two widely grown checks, Manoharsali and Jaya.

The crop was transplanted under rainfed lowland conditions at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 7.2-m² plots and three replications. No fertilizers or pesticides were applied. The experimental site had 587.4 kg available N/ha, 19.5 kg available P/ha, and 86.3 kg available K/ha.

Bogabordhan and Manoharsali were photoperiod-sensitive and Jaya was photoperiod-insensitive (see table). Bogabordhan outyielded both checks in grain yield, filled spikelet percentage, and 1,000-grain weight.

The variety had adequate field resistance to sheath rot and moderate resistance to bacterial blight, sheath blight, and false smut. Higher disease incidence in Jaya could be a reason for its

low percentage of filled spikelets (71%) and lower yield (3.4 t/ha) than other varieties. Bogabordhan yielded 45.2% more than Jaya (see table).

The lack of significance of the regression of yield across years indicates that Bogabordhan has the stability needed by resource-poor farmers. Bogabordhan's high yield of 4.5 t/ha coupled with its stability make it popular among farmers in Assam. ■

Performance of Bogabordhan and checks at Titabar, Assam, India, 1988-90 WS.

Character	Bogabordhan	Checks	
		Manoharsali (local)	Jaya
Photoperiod sensitivity	Sensitive	Sensitive	Insensitive
Plant height (cm)	141	139	99
Days to maturity (d)	145	149	131
Panicles/m ² (no.)	224	231	236
Lodging incidence ^a	1	9	3
Culm strength ^b	3	9	1
Panicle length (cm)	27	25	23
Spikelets/panicle (no.)	114	123	146
Filled spikelets (%)	96	91	71
1,000-grain wt (g)	29.9	25.6	24.3
Brown rice length (mm)	5.73	6.06	5.93
Brown rice width (mm)	2.93	2.53	2.19
Disease reaction ^c			
Bacterial blight	3	5	7
Sheath rot	1	3	5
Sheath blight	3	0	5
False smut	3	3	7
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.9	4.8	3.4
Regression coefficient (b) of yield on years ^d	0.022 ^{ns}	3.467*	-1.355*
Mean square deviations (s ² d)	0.25 ^{ns}	0.14 ^{ns}	0.20 ^{ns}
Increase in yield (%) in Bogabordhan over	-	1.2	45.2

^a1 = less than 20% area lodged, 3 = 20-40%, 9 = more than 80%. ^b1 = strong, 3 = moderately strong, 9 = very weak. ^c0 = highly resistant, 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible. ^dns = not significant, * = significant at the 5% level.

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Upland rice varieties Sita and Rimke released to farmers in Cambodia

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Upland rice is grown on only 2.5% (about 36,000 ha) of the area under rice in Cambodia. Most of these upland areas are in the provinces of Kampong Cham, Siem Reap, Kampong Thom, Mondul Kiri, Ratana Kiri, Kandal, Kampong Speu, and Stung Treng.

Because there are no recognized varieties for these rainfed uplands, we conducted a speedy varietal identification project using some research stations

and many farmers' fields. The trial was conducted during 1989 at four locations in Kandal, Kampong Speu, and Phnom Penh. During 1990 and 1991, we distributed many trial sets for on-farm testing. (See Table 1 for performance of the varieties.)

ITA150 is derived from the cross 63-83/(RO1, SE363G, Dourado Precoce) where the male parent was a mixture of pollen from three varieties. The breeding line was advanced with the pedigree TOX502-41-1-1. ITA257 is